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Wood-Based Bioelectronics: Lignosulfonate-Based Conductive Biocomposites for Paper Organic Electrochemical Transistors

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for sustainable diagnostic devices has shifted attention toward biodegradable choices in both material and substrate design. Recent advances in wood- and lignin-derived materials have enabled a growing class of sustainable electronic and bioelectronic systems, often referred to as ‘wood-based bioelectronics’. Within this context, the present work contributes a distinct materials and device strategy by integrating PEDOT:Lignosulfonate as an active mixed ionic–electronic channel material in organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) fabricated on biodegradable paper substrates. The PEDOT:LigS biocomposite was synthesized via chemical oxidative polymerization using various oxidants. The thin films of the resulting biocomposites exhibited good electrical conductivity of up to 1.1 S cm^{-1} , along with biocompatibility confirmed for L929 cells by following ISO 10993 standard protocol conditions. Conventional OECTs fabricated with PEDOT:LigS showed transconductance values of up to 12.9 mS. Replacing glass substrates with photographic paper enabled the fabrication of degradable OECT devices, revealing a material weight loss of 85% after 43 days in soil. These results highlight the potential of bio-based materials for more sustainable wood-based bioelectronics.

1 | Introduction

The growing demand for single-use, wearable, and biodegradable biomedical devices has brought attention not only to device performance but also to their health and environmental impact. Especially in the healthcare sector, disposable medical systems and point-of-care or personalized diagnostics devices generate large amounts of waste, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions. This highlights the necessity for sustainable materials and the development of innovative designs of biodegradable

diagnostics to minimize the environmental footprint of future healthcare technologies [1].

Bioelectronics based on bio-based and biocompatible materials have therefore become a major focus of research in recent years [2–4]. Especially, organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) are widely used in biomedical applications such as biosensing [5–7], neural interfaces [8], and wearable health monitoring [9, 10]. Their low operating voltage, biocompatibility, and ability to directly transduce ionic biological signals into electronic

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output make them highly attractive for next-generation bioelectronic devices [11]. OECT-based systems have been successfully implemented in point-of-care diagnostics, including SARS-CoV-2 detection [12] and uric acid sensing in human saliva [13]. Despite their great potential, conventional OECTs often rely on non-biodegradable or reusable polymeric substrates and synthetic materials, which pose challenges in terms of device disposal and recyclability [1, 14, 15]. Incorporating recyclable or biodegradable components into medical devices addresses both environmental and clinical concerns [1]. In this context, the development of OECTs on paper substrates reflects a simple approach for sensing applications [16–18]. A key challenge in paper-based bioelectronics is the inherent surface roughness of the substrate. Nevertheless, OECTs are comparatively less sensitive to this limitation than other device types [19]. Consequently, several studies have already explored paper-based OECTs, for example, using glossy photo paper coated with a polyethylene (PE) layer, as demonstrated by Mannerbro et al. [20], or various coated papers substrates, as reported by Bihar et al. [21].

At present, the most widely used organic mixed-ionic electronic conductor (OMIECs) in bioelectronics and biosensing is (poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):polystyrene sulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS) [22]. While this system has enabled high-performance OECTs, recent efforts have focused on transitioning to more naturally derived materials by replacing the synthetic polyanion PSS with naturally derived or biocompatible polyelectrolytes, such as double-stranded DNA [23, 24], sulfated cellulose nanocrystals [25, 26], hyaluronic acid [27], sacran [28], guar gum [22, 29], or polylactic acid [30]. Lignosulfonates (LigS) represent a particularly promising alternative counterion, as they combine polyanionic functionality with natural abundance, biodegradability and industrial relevance [31]. Lignin is the second most abundant natural polymer on Earth and, in contrast to cellulose, is largely a low-value by-product of the pulp and paper industry [31–34]. Depending on the extraction process, lignin can carry a range of functional groups, including aliphatic and phenolic hydroxyls, methoxyl, carbonyl, and carboxyl moieties (Figure 1) [32, 33, 35]. In sulfite pulping process, the wood is treated with sulfur dioxide (SO_2) and alkaline salts (e.g., Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , or NH_4^+), leading to depolymerization, condensation, and sulfonation reactions [31]. During this treatment, the solubility of lignin in water increases due to the introduction of strongly polar sulfonate groups, predominantly at the α -position of the benzylic carbon, allowing the separation of lignin from cellulose [33, 34, 36, 37]. The versatile structural and functional features of lignosulfonate (LigS) have enabled its use in a wide range of applications. Lignosulfonate-containing materials have previously been explored in biosensing and electronic systems [38, 39]. While wood-based electrochemical transistors exploit the intrinsic 3D architecture of wood as an active electronic scaffold [40], this work establishes PEDOT:Lignosulfonate as a viable bio-derived channel material for organic electrochemical transistors, extending lignin-based materials from passive or chemically responsive roles to active bioelectronic signal transduction. This altogether highlights lignin's potential as a bio-based substitute for PSS in PEDOT:PSS. Recently, PEDOT:LigS has been synthesized via oxidative chemical polymerization of EDOT in aqueous sodium lignosulfonate solutions, yielding a conductive biocomposite that has been explored in energy

storage and sensing applications. For instance, PEDOT:LigS has been employed as an electrode material in supercapacitors [41] and sodium-ion batteries [42], where the quinone groups in lignin contribute additional pseudocapacitance. In this context, Li et al. also reported PEDOT:LigS gel-based supercapacitors, using a LigS-PEDOT/poly(acrylamide) hydrogel as the electrode [43]. Hydrogel-based PEDOT:LigS electrodes have been employed in wearable strain sensors capable of detecting weak physiological signals, such as pulse and throat vibrations [44]. Beyond electronics, lignin-based materials, including LigS composites, have been studied for biomedical applications ranging from drug delivery systems to antibacterial hydrogels prepared with sodium alginate, polyacrylamide, or chitosan [45, 46]. In this respect, several lignin composites have demonstrated good biocompatibility with mammalian cell lines such as mouse fibroblasts [46], rat neuronal cells [47], human dermal fibroblasts [47], vascular endothelial cells [48], and mesenchymal stem cells [47], supporting the potential of LigS as a biocompatible PSS substitute for biomedical applications [35].

Here, we report a conductive biocomposite, PEDOT:Lignosulfonate (PEDOT:LigS), as the channel polymer for potentially degradable paper-based OECTs. Figure 1A presents a workflow diagram visually maps out the steps of overall process. We prepared the functional composite materials with high electrical conductivity via in-situ oxidative chemical polymerization using two different oxidants, ferric tosylate ($\text{Fe}(\text{Tos})_3$) and ammonium persulfate (APS). Particle size and morphological analysis were performed by dynamic light-scattering (DLS) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) techniques, respectively. To enhance the sustainability aspect, photographic-quality paper was utilized as a cellulose-based OECT substrate. The PEDOT:LigS-based OECTs, fabricated through a facile, non-lithographic, and etch-free process, exhibited promising steady-state electrical performance. A proof-of-concept degradation study in water-wetted soil demonstrated that the paper-based OECTs lost 85% of their initial weight within 43 days, highlighting their potential for biodegradable electronics. Furthermore, the biocomposite showed good biocompatibility with murine fibroblast cells, as confirmed by flow cytometry analysis performed in accordance with the ISO 10993 protocol.

Overall, this study introduces PEDOT:LigS as a bio-based material with potential for more sustainable and a biocompatible alternative to PEDOT:PSS for OECTs for a contribution to the growing field of wood-based bioelectronics. These findings lay the groundwork for future developments of conductive lignosulfonate composites in bioelectronics, sensing, and biomedical applications.

2 | Results and Discussion

According to previous reports, PEDOT:LigS has been synthesized via oxidative chemical polymerization [41–43, 49]. In this work, the synthesis was performed using iron(III) *p*-toluenesulfonate ($\text{Fe}(\text{Tos})_3$) and ammonium persulfate (APS) as oxidants (see Supporting Information S1). The negatively charged sulfonate groups of lignosulfonate (LigS) stabilize the positively charged PEDOT chains, thereby improving their dispersibility and processability

FIGURE 1 | A Schematic illustration of the overall process: In the first pathway, lignosulfonic acid sodium salt (LigS) is used for the synthesis of the conductive biocomposite PEDOT:LigS. In parallel, commercially available photography paper is used as the cellulose-derived substrate after removing its top coloured polymer layer. Both wood-derived components are then combined to fabricate organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs), which can be electrically characterized using an additional polymer well as a reservoir for the electrolyte. Finally, the lifecycle closes with a degradation study, where the OECT devices are incubated in water-wetted soil. B Molecular structure of i) lignosulfonic acid sodium salt and ii) the PEDOT:LigS biocomposite.

FIGURE 2 | XPS spectra of PEDOT:LigS synthesized using Fe(Tos)₃ or APS as the oxidant. A XPS survey spectrum for PEDOT:LigS (3:1 wt. ratio, using Fe(Tos)₃) with the corresponding high-resolution scans for B C1s and C S2p. D XPS survey spectrum of PEDOT:LigS (6:1 wt. ratio, using APS) with the respective high-resolution scans for E C1s and F S2p.

FIGURE 3 | ATR-FTIR spectra of the reference materials PEDOT:Tos (black line) and sodium lignosulfonate (LigS, orange line), as well as for a representative of the prepared biocomposites, namely PEDOT:LigS (3:1 initial weight ratio, brown line), synthesized with APS as oxidant.

in aqueous media. This charge stabilization effectively overcomes the intrinsically poor water solubility of PEDOT, making the combination of LigS as an ionically conductive matrix and PEDOT as the electronic conductor highly suitable for various OMIEC applications.

2.1 | Spectroscopic Characterization

To verify the presence of both components in the prepared biocomposite, x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and attenuated total reflection Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) analysis were performed. XPS analysis confirmed the presence of C, O, and S elements in the biocomposite for both synthesis routes (see Figure 2A,D). The high-resolution C1s spectrum

was deconvoluted into four component peaks at 283.6, 284.8, 285.8, and 288.0 eV. These peaks can be attributed to: (i) C=C bonds at the β -position of the EDOT unit and aromatic structures in the lignin backbone, (ii) C–C bonds associated with the aromatic rings of EDOT and lignin, (iii) C–O–C bonds present in both EDOT and the ether functionalities of lignin, and (iv) C=O bonds characteristic of carbonyl groups in lignin, such as those within phenylpropanoid moieties [43, 50, 51]. The deconvoluted S2p spectrum displayed four peaks at 162.7,

163.9, 165.5, and 166.6 eV, corresponding to the S2p_{3/2} and S2p_{1/2} spin-orbit doublets of the PEDOT backbone, as well as the S2p_{3/2} and S2p_{1/2} components of the -SO₃⁻ groups derived from lignosulfonate [49]. Importantly, no residual Fe²⁺ ions were detected in the material (Supporting Information S2). The values in the S2p high-resolution spectrum for the APS-based material are slightly shifted ~0.15 eV to lower energies. A complete summary of the elemental composition of the XPS survey scans is provided in Supporting Information S2. To further verify that the detected -SO₃⁻ groups originated from lignosulfonate rather than from the sulfur-containing oxidant, PEDOT:LigS was additionally synthesized using FeCl₃. The resulting material exhibited similar sulfonate-related signals in the deconvoluted S2p spectrum as those obtained for the other oxidants (Supporting Information S2).

Furthermore, ATR-FTIR spectra were recorded for the reference materials PEDOT:Tos and pure sodium lignosulfonate, as well as for PEDOT:LigS prepared with an initial 3:1 wt. ratio (Figure 3). The obtained sodium lignosulfonate (LigS) spectrum closely matched previously reported data, with minor shifts in peak positions and changes in absorption intensity arising from differences in the origin of the lignosulfonate and batch-to-batch variations. In general, the band at 3406 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to -OH stretching vibrations, the peaks at 1600 and 1433 cm⁻¹ to C–C stretching vibrations of the aromatic backbone, the bands at 1106 and 957 cm⁻¹ to the guaiacyl units, and the peak at 618 cm⁻¹ to S–O bond vibrations [52, 53]. In the biocomposite spectrum, a broad band at 3263 cm⁻¹ can be clearly assigned to O–H stretching vibrations of sodium lignosulfonate. Overall, the PEDOT:LigS spectrum appears as a superposition of the two reference spectra, with several bands slightly shifted from their original positions. In addition, the composite exhibits a characteristic C–S bond absorption in the 1500–500 cm⁻¹ region, commonly referred to as the doping-induced infrared active vibration (IRAV) band [28, 54]. ATR-FTIR spectra of PEDOT:LigS samples prepared with varying weight ratios and oxidant systems are provided in Supporting Information S3.

2.2 | Morphological Characterization

The particle sizes of PEDOT:LigS composites synthesized with different initial weight ratios and oxidants are summarized in Table 1. In general, biocomposites prepared with Fe(Tos)₃ display larger particle or agglomerate sizes, with increasing PEDOT content further promoting particle growth, reaching up to 734 ± 66 nm at a 6:1 wt. ratio. In contrast, APS-based composites displayed significantly smaller particle sizes, averaging 396 ± 26 nm. The differences in hydrodynamic size between APS- and Fe(Tos)₃-derived dispersions can be rationalized by nucleation–growth kinetics. APS thermally generates sulfate radicals (SO₄•⁻), and higher radical flux generally increases the number of nucleation events (reaction loci), which can lead to smaller particles and shorter chains due to more frequent termination [55]. In contrast, Fe(III) tosylate oxidatively polymerizes EDOT via electron transfer to form EDOT radical cations, with chain growth occurring through oxidative coupling while Fe(III) is reduced to Fe(II); tosylate serves as the counterion/dopant [56]. Under otherwise comparable conditions, this can yield a lower effective nucleation density and greater growth/aggregation per nucleus, consistent

TABLE 1 | An overview of the measured particle size distribution of the biocomposite with different initial EDOT:LigS weight ratios as well as for the different oxidants used.

Material	Oxidant	EDOT:LigS wt. ratio	D_h /nm	PDI	n
PEDOT:LigS	Fe(Tos) ₃	3:1	460 ± 26	0.389 ± 0.047	9
PEDOT:LigS		6:1	735 ± 66	0.419 ± 0.094	15
PEDOT:LigS	APS	3:1	313 ± 16	0.397 ± 0.043	5
PEDOT:LigS		6:1	396 ± 26	0.322 ± 0.085	9
PEDOT:Tos (control) ^a	Fe(Tos) ₃	—	680 ± 31	0.309 ± 0.068	5

^aPEDOT:Tos. material characterization results obtained from Matura et al. (2025) [28].

FIGURE 4 | SEM images of PEDOT:LigS (weight-to-weight ratio of 6:1) with the standard additives (0.5% DBSA, 5% Glycerol and 1% overall GOPS) using Fe(Tos)₃ as oxidant in A and C, whereas for B and D APS was used for the polymerization. The scale bars are 500 nm for the higher and 5 μm for the lower magnification of the images, respectively.

with the larger particle sizes observed for Fe(Tos)₃-derived samples.

To investigate the morphological characteristics of the synthesized materials, SEM images were acquired for PEDOT:LigS (6:1 initial wt. ratio) prepared using either Fe(Tos)₃ or APS as the oxidant (Figure 4). The SEM micrographs revealed the characteristic granular and globular morphology typical of PEDOT-based materials [23, 28]. For both synthesis routes, the biocomposite thin films contained the additives 4-dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid (DBSA), glycerol, and (3-glycidyoxypropyl)trimethoxysilane (GOPs), which were incorporated to improve film formation, enhance electrical conductivity, and prevent delamination [57]. Notably, the Fe(Tos)₃-based films exhibited slightly larger aggregates and a coarser granular texture compared to the APS-based films. This observation is consistent with the DLS results showing a larger average particle size for Fe(Tos)₃-derived samples. The same additive-containing dispersions were subsequently employed for conductivity measurements and device

fabrication to ensure consistent material properties across all experiments.

2.3 | PEDOT:LigS-Based OECTs on Glass Substrate

To evaluate the feasibility of the prepared PEDOT:LigS biocomposite for OECT applications, its electrical conductivity was first investigated. The corresponding values obtained at the highest initial EDOT-to-lignosulfonate ratio, synthesized using either Fe(Tos)₃ or APS as oxidants, are summarized in Table 2. Among these, the thin films prepared from the PEDOT:LigS dispersions, synthesized with Fe(Tos)₃ as oxidant, exhibited the highest conductivity, reaching 1.1 S cm⁻¹ (± 0.43 S cm⁻¹). Additional conductivity data for varying oxidants and initial weight ratios are provided in Supporting Information S4. Interestingly, the material synthesized with Fe(Tos)₃ achieved higher electrical conductivity than APS-based thin films. As explained in the section above, Fe(Tos)₃ can promote more extensive chain growth

TABLE 2 | Overview of the OECT device parameters including maximum transconductance (g_{max}), the OECT channel thickness (d), the normalized transconductance (g_{max} (NR)), the voltage corresponding to the g_{max} and the conductivity of prepared PEDOT:LigS thin films (6:1 wt. ratio), whereby the respective biocomposite dispersion synthesized with different oxidants during chemical polymerization.

Material (Substrate)	Oxidant	Film Conductivity ^a	g_{max}/mS	d (OECT)/ μm	g_{max} (NR)/S cm^{-1}	$V_{g,max}/V$	On/Off ratio	N ^b
		/S cm^{-1}						
PEDOT:LigS (glass)	Fe(Tos) ₃	1.10 ± 0.43 ^b	0.32 ± 0.11	0.41 ± 0.04	0.19 ± 0.03	-0.311 ± 0.02	37 ± 8	[7]
PEDOT: LigS (glass)	APS	0.65 ± 0.35 ^c	0.14 ± 0.13	0.40 ± 0.07	0.09 ± 0.05	-0.39 ± 0.14	14 ± 9	[7]
PEDOT:LigS (paper)	Fe(Tos) ₃	—	0.55 ± 0.28	~0.4	0.18 ± 0.07	-0.29 ± 0.01	91 ± 43	[5]
PEDOT:LigS (paper)	APS	—	0.13 ± 0.11	~0.4	0.06 ± 0.02	-0.26 ± 0.01	44 ± 19	[5]
PEDOT:PSS ^a (PH1000) [28] (glass)	—	357 ± 1.7	33.1 ± 5.3	—	22.5 ± 5.2	0.21 ± 0.07	8 ± 4	[12]

^aPEDOT:PSS OECT device results obtained from Matura et al. (2025) [28];

^bElectrical conductivity was measured from 10 substrates with three to four measurement points each ($n = 32$);

^cElectrical conductivity was measured from 16 substrates with three to four measurement points each ($n = 59$).

and the formation of larger, more interconnected networks in thin films [58]. These larger, well-connected polymer domains are favorable for electronic percolation and charge transport [58], which is consistent with the higher electrical conductivity observed for Fe(Tos)₃-based films. In contrast, APS-derived sulfate radicals are expected to generate a higher density of initiation sites, leading to smaller domains and increased structural disorder, which can limit long-range charge transport.

The conductivities obtained in this work are comparable to those reported for other PEDOT-based biocomposites. For example, PEDOT:sulfated nanocellulose [25] exhibited conductivities of around 5 S cm^{-1} , while PEDOT:Sacran [28] reached up to 1.88 S cm^{-1} . In contrast, the Lignosulfonate-PEDOT-polyacrylamide hydrogel [43] demonstrated a lower conductivity of 0.5, whereas PEDOT:PSS combined with conductive wood veneers [59] achieved 2.0 S cm^{-1} . Additionally, PEDOT:lignosulfonate films doped with perfluorooctanoic acid were reported to exhibit a conductivity of 0.12 S cm^{-1} [60].

After evaluating the conductivity, the PEDOT:LigS biocomposite was employed as channel material in organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs). A schematic cross-section of the device architecture is shown in Figure 5A. Chromium/Gold (Cr/Au) was used for the source and drain electrodes, a non-polarizable Ag/AgCl electrode served as the gate, and 50 mM phosphate buffer saline (PBS, pH 7.2) was used as the electrolyte solution. A uniform PEDOT:LigS layer was spin-coated onto the substrate, forming the active channel (Figure 5B). The first set of devices were fabricated on glass substrates, using dispersions synthesized with either Fe(Tos)₃ or APS as oxidants. The corresponding transfer characteristics are shown in Figure 5C (Fe(Tos)₃) and Figure 5D (APS). Under steady-state operation, the transfer curve of an OECT represents the drain current (I_D) as a function of the applied gate voltage (V_G) at constant drain voltage (V_D). The first derivative of this curve defines the transconductance ($g_m = \partial I_D / \partial V_G$), which is a key figure of merit for OECTs quantifying

the amplification capability of the device when converting ionic signals into electronic output.

To account for variations in channel geometry and thickness, the maximum transconductance was normalized according to Equation (1), [61]:

$$g_{max}(NR) = g_{max} \cdot \frac{L}{d \cdot W} \quad (1)$$

where L is defined as the channel length, d as the channel thickness, and W as the channel width.

For the PEDOT:LigS OECTs, the expected behavior typical of p-type materials such as PEDOT:PSS was observed: as the gate voltage (V_G) decreased, the absolute drain current ($I_D I$) increased, while at higher V_G values, the current approached zero, corresponding to the device's off-state. Devices prepared from Fe(Tos)₃-based dispersions exhibited a higher average normalized transconductance of 0.19 S cm^{-1} , compared to 0.09 S cm^{-1} for APS-based devices. These values are slightly higher than those previously reported for PEDOT:Sacran OECTs (0.11 S cm^{-1}) [28], yet remain below those of PEDOT:sulfated cellulose nanocrystals devices (2.4 S cm^{-1}) [25]. The output characteristics (I_D vs. V_D), at different constant V_G values, are shown in Figure 5E,F. In both cases, $I_D I$ increased with decreasing V_D and reached a near-saturation regime at approximately -0.7 V. This behavior is a characteristic of p-doped OECTs channel polymers operated in depletion mode [61]. In order to further enhance the maximum transconductance, thicker films were prepared via drop-casting. Thereby, maximum g_m values of 12.9 and 9.0 mS were achieved for approximately 6 μm Fe(Tos)₃-based and 6.5 μm APS-based films, respectively. On average, the OECTs fabricated using Fe(Tos)₃-based PEDOT:LigS exhibited normalized g_m values of 0.34 S cm^{-1} , while those based on APS-derived dispersions achieved 0.17 S cm^{-1} . Compared with PEDOT:PSS (Table 2), PEDOT:LigS likely exhibits a less optimized balance between

FIGURE 5 | Characterization of PEDOT:LigS-based OECTs on glass substrates. A A schematic depiction of the general cross-section of the OECT device, including the Cr/Au source-drain electrodes, the non-polarizable Ag/AgCl gate electrode and the PEDOT:LigS as channel material. B A photo of the source-drain electrode structures with a thin film of deposited PEDOT:LigS biocomposite (Scale bar = 1 mm). C Transfer characteristics with the corresponding transconductance curve (for $V_D = -0.7$ V) and E the respective output characteristics for 6:1 wt. ratio PEDOT:LigS ($\text{Fe}(\text{Tos})_3$) based-OECT devices ($W = 2.1$ mm, $L = 64$ μm , $d = 400$ nm). D Transfer characteristics with the respective transconductance curve (for $V_D = -0.7$ V) and F the respective output characteristics for 6:1 wt. ratio PEDOT:LigS (APS) based-OECT devices ($W = 2.1$ mm, $L = 65$ μm , $d = 260$ nm).

electronic percolation and ionic accessibility due to the heterogeneous, polydisperse nature of lignosulfonate, leading to lower effective volumetric doping capability and reduced switching performance.

2.4 | Biodegradable Paper-Based OECTs

To address the sustainability challenge posed by common transient devices, particularly their degradability, a readily previously used photographic-quality paper was selected as a cellulose-based substrate for device fabrication. The resulting paper-based OECTs devices are shown in Figure 6D, and their corresponding device performance is presented in Figure 6A,B. A detailed examination of Table 2 reveals that, prior to normalization, the g_m values of $\text{Fe}(\text{Tos})_3$ -based OECTs fabricated on paper substrates reach up to 0.55 S cm^{-1} , exceeding those obtained on glass. This variation underlines the need to normalize transconductance values with respect to the channel geometry, as minor deviations can arise from batch-to-batch variations in the Cr/Au deposition process, as well as from slight differences in the channel film thickness. For the thin films deposited on paper, a thickness of approximately 400 nm was estimated for the same spin-coating procedure, since the increased surface roughness of the paper makes an exact determination challenging. After normalization, the OECTs on paper substrates exhibited average normalized g_m values of 0.18 and 0.06 S cm^{-1} for the $\text{Fe}(\text{Tos})_3$ - and APS-based dispersions, respectively, which demonstrates that their performance is comparable to that of devices fabricated on glass substrates (Table 2).

The device processing was facilitated by the thin protective coating on the paper surface, which produced a moderately hydrophobic surface with a water contact angle of $91.6^\circ \pm 1.5^\circ$, as shown in Figure 6C. The FTIR measurement shown in Supporting Information S7 suggests that the protective layer on the paper substrate corresponds to a polymeric wax coating [62, 63].

To further demonstrate the device concept aligned with sustainability-oriented materials design, a proof-of-concept degradation study was conducted. Monitoring degradation through weight loss measurements has been a common approach in evaluating the biodegradability of various substrates under soil conditions [64–66]. In this study, paper-based OECTs were incubated in water-saturated soil at 50°C for up to two months, and their weight loss was monitored over time. After 26 days, the devices had lost approximately 75% of their initial weight, after which the degradation slowed considerably (Figure 6E). By day 43, a total weight loss of 85% was observed, with the remaining 15% corresponding primarily to the residual protective polymer layer (Figure 6F). Yang et al. [67], previously reported that shellac-coated silicon wafers immersed in PBS at 37°C for 11–30 days exhibited leaching of shellac components and a reduction in molecular weight due to hydrolytic degradation, while the coatings themselves remained visibly intact [67]. In future studies, the current protective layer can be easily replaced with naturally degradable alternatives such as shellac-based [68], beeswax [69, 70] or carnauba wax [71, 72] coatings, rendering the substrate fully biodegradable. Nevertheless, even in its current configuration, this approach underscores the simplicity of fabrication of

FIGURE 6 | Characterization of paper OEETs. A Transfer characteristic of an exemplary paper OEET with the corresponding calculated transconductance curve (for $V_D = -0.7$ V) and B the respective output characteristics ($W = 2.2$ mm, $L = 22$ μ m, $d = \sim 400$ nm). C Contact angle measurement using 18 M Ω water on the paper substrate (droplet volume: 10 μ L). D Picture of a paper OEET under operation (Scale bar = 0.7 cm). E Weight loss (%) for cellulose biodegradation via microbial/enzymatic activity in soil. F Images of the degradation experiment taken of individual sample after the period t of incubation at 50°C in water-wetted soil.

paper-based OEETs exhibiting device-level disintegration under soil-burial conditions. Consistent with the literature for biodegradation as microbial breakdown into innocuous components and given the presence of microorganisms in soil, [64, 65] the observed mass loss and device disintegration are appropriately described as biodegradation.

In the literature, PEDOT:PSS-based OEETs have been fabricated on various biodegradable substrates, including cellulose paper [16], chemically modified cellulose paper [73, 74], PLGA [75, 76], and PLA [14]. However, among these studies, only Wu *et al.* and Fumeaux *et al.* reported device degradation for PLGA-based [76] and PLA-based OEETs¹⁴, respectively. In addition, biodegradable OEETs fabricated on PLA with a channel thickness (d) comparable to that used in our study exhibited a transconductance of up to ~ 0.25 mS [14] (see Table 3).

In the present work, PEDOT:LigS channel materials deposited on paper exhibited a transconductance (g_m) of 0.27 mS, which is comparable to our previous results obtained on flexible PLA substrates [28]. The biodegradation behavior of PLA- and paper-based OEETs incorporating novel biocomposite materials represents a fundamental step toward sustainable bioelectronics.

2.5 | Biocompatibility Study of PEDOT:LigS

Beyond its bio-based origin, the biocomposite also demonstrates strong potential for biocompatibility in Figure 7. For this purpose, a 3:1 weight ratio of EDOT to liginosulfonate was selected using the Fe(Tos)₃-based dispersion, which was identified as the best-performing oxidant system. This composition allows the

TABLE 3 | Flexible paper-based and biodegradable OECTs for bioelectronic applications.

Channel Material	Substrate	Degradation Test	g_m/mS	$L/\mu m$	$W/\mu m$	$d/\mu m$	$g_m(NR)/S\ cm^{-1}$	Application	Refs.
PEDOT:PSS	Paper	—	40.1	500	1000	5.63	35.6	H ₂ O ₂ and glucose sensor	[16]
PEDOT:PSS	Hydrophobic Filter Paper	—	0.9	100	230	—	—	Multianalyte point-of-care sensor	[73]
PEDOT:PSS	Nitrocellulose	—	4	170	350	5	3.9	Dopamine oxidation sensor	[74]
PEDOT:PSS	PLGA ^a	—	3.2	30	1000	0.2	4.8	Electrocardiographic measurements	[75]
PEDOT:PSS	PLGA ^a (12 μm)	Degradation in PBS, at 90°C	8.67	20	200	0.2	43.35	Transient spatiotemporal monitoring of neural activity	[76]
PEDOT:PSS	PLA ^b	Degradation in soil	0.247	3000	1000	0.5	14.82	Biodegradable OECT	[14]
PEDOT:Sacran	PLA ^b (20 μm)	Enzymatic biodegradation, in PBS, 37°C	1.6	35	2200	~ 9.5	0.03	Flexible and biodegradable OECT	[28] Previous Work*
PEDOT:LigS	Paper	Wetted-soil burial, at 50°C	0.27	64	2100	0.4	0.21	Wood-based biodegradable OECTs	This Work**

^aPoly(lactic-co-glycolic acid);^b Poly (lactic acid).

assessment of higher lignin content, given that PEDOT itself has previously been shown to exhibit low cytotoxicity [24]. In vitro staining with propidium iodide (PI) for dead cells and calcein-AM for healthy cells was employed as a simple yet effective screening method to evaluate biocompatibility. The extract toxicity and cell testing, grown directly on the PEDOT:LigS surface, were performed according to the ISO 10993 standard protocols for evaluating the cytotoxicity of new materials. For extracts this method examines the potential release of soluble compounds, degradation products, or leachables into the culture medium, simulating the indirect exposure that would occur in vivo when the device interacts with surrounding tissues and fluids. The tested samples did not reduce cell viability either under direct contact with the PEDOT:LigS composite thin-films or after incubation with their 24-h extracts in culture medium (see Figure 7F). Moreover, fluorescent microscopy images of cells grown 24 h and 72 h in extracts or in direct contact on PEDOT:LigS show the same morphology and calcein green fluorescence as control cells (Figure 7A–E). These findings are consistent with the reported high biocompatibility of related materials containing PEDOT [24] and lignin designed for biological applications [44, 77]. This result represents an initial screening and does not establish long-term or implantable biocompatibility.

While PEDOT and PEDOT-based biocomposites have consistently shown low acute cytotoxicity and good cellular compatibility [24, 28], conventional conducting polymers are generally not intrinsically biodegradable and may persist unless incorporated

into biodegradable matrices or transient device architectures [78]. Recent studies on biologically assisted disintegration of PEDOT-containing organic transistor suggest that such systems can physically break down without observable adverse environmental effects [79]. Although complete mineralization of PEDOT fragments has not yet been demonstrated, they suggest that PEDOT-based materials can be incorporated into transient electronic systems without generating acutely harmful by products.

3 | Conclusion

In this work, we synthesized a PEDOT:LigS biocomposite using two different oxidants and confirmed the presence of both components through XPS and FTIR analysis. The resulting material exhibited electrical conductivity comparable to other reported conductive biocomposites. By employing PEDOT:LigS as the channel polymer in OECTs, we demonstrated its strong potential for bioelectronic applications. Furthermore, degradation studies in water-wetted soil revealed that paper-based OECTs incorporating PEDOT:LigS as the channel material lost up to 85% of weight within 43 days. In addition, PEDOT:LigS showed good biocompatibility with L929 fibroblast cells, as verified under ISO 10993 standard protocol conditions. Overall, the combination of a lignosulfonate-based conductive biocomposite with cellulose-based photographic paper presents a promising strategy toward more sustainable and biodegradable wood-based bioelectronics. Systematic investigations of operational stability and cycling

FIGURE 7 | Evaluation of the biocompatibility of PEDOT:LigS samples according to ISO 10993. Fluorescence microscopy images of control cells incubated for (A) 24 h and (B) 72 h, and cells in direct contact with PEDOT:LigS films after (C) 24 h and (D) 72 h of incubation. (E) Fluorescence microscopy images of cells cultured with extracts obtained after 24 h of incubation. Extracts refer to culture medium that was incubated with the PEDOT:LigS samples for 24 h, subsequently collected, and then used to culture L929 cells seeded in commercial plastic chambers for an additional 24 h. Scale bars: 200 μm. (F) Cell viability (%) quantified using a LIVE/DEAD Viability/Cytotoxicity kit. h hha h h)h.

endurance, together with biosensing demonstrations, will be addressed in future studies.

4 | Methods

4.1 | Materials

3,4-Ethylenedioxythiophene (EDOT, 99%) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Iron (III) *p*-toluenesulfonate hexahydrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{Tos})_3$), ammonium persulfate (APS), and lignosulfonic acid sodium salt (LigS, average $M_w \sim 52,000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. The solution additives 4-dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid (DBSA), glycerol and (3-glycidioxypropyl) trimethoxysilane (GOPS) were acquired from Fluka, Carl Roth and Grolman, respectively. Commercial poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene): poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS, Clevis PH 1000) was obtained from Heraeus Electronics GmbH (Hanau, Germany). Prior to usage, the PEDOT:PSS

dispersion was filtered through a polyvinylidene fluoride filter with a pore size of 0.45 μm. All other reagents were used as received without further purification.

Purified 18 MΩ ultrapure water was obtained by the Arium Mini laboratory water system.

4.2 | Synthesis of PEDOT:Lignosulfonate (PEDOT:LigS)

Following the synthesis procedure described by Matura et al. [25, 28], first the ligninsulfonic acid sodium salt (LigS) was dissolved in 18 MΩ water in a concentration of 5 mg mL⁻¹. The solution was then stirred until the material was fully dissolved, resulting in a brown solution. As a next step, the EDOT monomer was injected in the different respective weight-to-weight ratios of monomer to LigS (1:1, 3:1 and 6:1), followed by a sonication step using a tip sonicator (60 W, 0.6 s pulse) for 10 min. Subsequently,

2.5 molar equiv. of iron (III) *p*-toluene sulfonate hexahydrate (Fe(Tos)₃) or ammonium peroxydisulfate (APS) or iron (III) chloride (FeCl₃) (with respect to EDOT) was added into the mixture. The dispersion was stirred for 1 h at room temperature and then heated to 50°C for 4–5 h under continuous stirring. The resulting dark blue dispersion was then further diluted with MΩ water and centrifuged at a speed of 5500 rpm for 3 min, followed by re-dispersion in fresh MΩ water. This step was repeated until the pH of the dispersion was neutralized. Then, the dispersion was dialyzed for 24 h using a dialysis membrane with a molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) of 12–14 kDa. The dialysis water was periodically changed. The purified material was then dried using a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure (50–200 mbar). The obtained product was a blackish-blue powder, which was stored at 4°C until further use.

4.3 | Synthesis of PEDOT

Tosylate (PEDOT:Tos.) was performed by following the same preparation procedure as PEDOT:LigS. The oxidative chemical polymerization was also conducted using only EDOT with iron (III) *p*-toluene sulfonate as the oxidant in 2.5 molar equiv. Within this procedure, no LigS was included. The tosylate (Tos) anion from the oxidant acts as a doping counterion and stabilizes the oxidized cationic PEDOT [28].

4.4 | Material Characterization

Attenuated Total Reflectance—Fourier-transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectra were recorded using a Bruker Vertex 80 FTIR spectrometer equipped with a Bruker Platinum diamond attenuated total reflectance (ATR) unit. The biocomposite powder or other dispersion were measured after drying.

x-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed on a Theta Probe XPS-system (ThermoFisher, GBR). The specimens were probed with monochromated Al Kα x-Ray radiation (1486.6 eV) focused into a spot of 200 μm in diameter to ensure a good signal-to-noise ratio. Survey spectra were acquired using a pass energy of 200 eV (and 40 eV for high resolution core level) and a binding energy (BE) step of 1 eV (0.05 eV), respectively. To compensate for charges accumulating at the surface, a dual flood gun emitting Ar-Ions with low kinetic energy was in use. The measured spectra were corrected with respect to the C1s peak of the adventitious carbon at 284.8 eV. Evaluation was performed using the Avantage software package provided by the device manufacturer. For the XPS characterization, the original stock dispersions (PEDOT:LigS) were used without further additives, whereby the dispersions were drop-cast on a glass slide and fully dried.

Particle Size Measurements were conducted using a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZSP (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Worcestershire, UK). The dynamic light scattering (DLS) method was utilized to determine the particle size distribution. The DLS measurements via intensity were performed at 25°C, filling 1.1 mL of the sample into a disposable cuvette (DTS0012). To prepare the sample dispersions, 1 mg was diluted with 2 mL of MΩ water and then sonicated for 10 min using an ultrasonic processor set to 60 W

with a 0.6 s pulse. Afterward, the sample dispersions were further diluted by transferring 0.5 mL of the prepared sample into 2 mL of MΩ water. This final sample was sonicated again under the same conditions, and then at least 6 measurements were recorded for each type of sample.

Higher particle size values (above 1000 nm) were dismissed due to possible aggregation effects leading to miscalculations.

4.5 | Thin-Film Characterization

First, glass substrates (1.5 cm x 1.5 cm) and ITO-coated glass (1.27 cm x 1.27 cm) were cleaned following a successive cleaning procedure starting with a 2% (v/v) aqueous solution of Hellmanex III, deionized water, acetone and isopropanol at 50°C in an ultrasonic bath for 20 min each. Before further usage, the substrates were blow-dried with N₂ gas and then treated with oxygen plasma at 75 W for 5 min in an AutoGlow Plasma System. For the absorption spectroscopy and conductivity samples of composites, a mixture of 94.5% (v/v) dispersion (PEDOT:LigS in different weight ratios), 0.5% (v/v) DBSA, and 5% (v/v) glycerol was prepared, whereby subsequently 1% (v/v) GOPS was added into the dispersion. Finally, the deposition of the biocomposite dispersions on glass was performed using either drop-casting for conductivity measurements or spin-coating for biocompatibility measurements.

The conductivity of the films was measured using an Ossila four-point probe station with supplied software for evaluation.

Contact Angle Tests were performed to evaluate the surface hydrophobicity of paper substrates. Multiple 18 MΩ water droplets were measured at room temperature using an Ossila Contact Angle Goniometer and the average values were determined.

Field Emission-Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) analyses were performed on a FEI FEG-Quanta 450 instrument (Field Electron and Ion Company, Hillsboro, OR, USA). The PEDOT:LigS dispersions with and without additives were spin-coated on cleaned ITO-coated glass substrates for the SEM measurements. The samples were sputtered with platinum before analysis. The micrographs were taken at 10 000x and 100 000x magnification.

4.6 | OECT Device Fabrication and Characterization

For the fabrication of the organic electrochemical transistor (OECT), first, the source-drain electrode pattern (channel length: L = 60 μm, channel width W = 2 mm) was prepared by fixing cleaned glass substrates onto a shadow mask (thickness = 200 μm). Next, 10 nm Cr and 100 nm Au were deposited successively by thermal evaporation at a pressure of 1–5 × 10⁻⁷ mbar. Afterward, the channel was formed by spin-coating a thin film of the respective sample dispersion (PEDOT:LigS) at 900 rpm for 40 s, followed by 1 200 rpm for 10 s. The regions surrounding the channel and the contacts were then carefully cleaned with water-moistened cotton swabs. Finally,

the substrates were annealed at 120°C for 30 min. To increase the film thickness, the spin-coating process was repeated, with a brief annealing step of 2 min at 120°C applied in place of the final 30 min annealing at 120°C. For producing thicker channel layers of approximately 10 μm, the dispersions were drop-cast onto the channel structure rather than spin-coated, followed by drying at 100°C for 10 min and a final annealing step at 120°C for 20 min.

To finalize the devices, a laser-cut polymer well made of 3M VHB tape (acrylic adhesive with a conformable acrylic foam core) was attached to the substrates to contain the aqueous electrolyte. For characterization, 20 μL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, 50 mM, pH 7.4) was applied, and a silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) electrode served as the non-polarizable gate electrode. All steady-state current–voltage measurements were conducted under ambient conditions using an Agilent E5273A. To enhance the contact between the measurement pins and the Au electrodes, a small amount of silver paste (Leitsilber 200, Ögussa) was applied to the Au source/drain contacts.

A Bruker Dektak XT profilometer with a stylus force of 2 mg was utilized to measure the film thickness.

Microscope images for the channel geometries were recorded using a Nikon Eclipse LV100 ND microscope in bright-field mode.

4.7 | Fabrication of Degradable Paper Substrate OECTs

First, the top light-sensitive polymer (colored) layer of common microporous luster photography-quality paper was carefully removed. Then, the paper substrates (thickness ~ 200 μm) were fixed on 25.4 mm by 9 mm glass substrates using double-sided Kapton tape (3M), whereby the bottom side of the photographic paper was used as the active surface for the coating. The OECT devices on paper were prepared by applying the same processing steps described above for glass substrates. The only difference was that the paper substrates were not wiped after the spin-coating step. At the end the paper OECT was removed from the Kapton tape.

Degradation Tests of the paper OECTs were performed using composted soil (peat-free plant soil, SPAR), which was sieved prior to use. The soil was placed into flasks and moistened with water, after which the fabricated paper OECTs were positioned inside and covered with an additional soil layer. Each flask was then watered again and sealed with a screw lid before being incubated in an oven at approximately 50°C. At predefined time intervals (10, 18, 26 and 43 days), individual flasks were opened and their contents removed. The degraded devices were carefully cleaned with water to eliminate residual soil, dried, and subsequently weighed. The percentage weight loss ($W_L\%$) is calculated using Equation (2):

$$W_L\% = \frac{(W_i - W_f)}{W_i} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

where W_i and W_f are the respective initial and the final mass of the sample.

4.8 | Cell Viability—Direct Contact

The tested materials were sterilized in 70% ethanol and placed at the bottom of the wells of the standard 24-well plate. L929 cells (adipose mouse fibroblasts) were obtained from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA). Cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM, Life Technologies, Carlsbad, CA, USA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum, 2 mM L-Glutamine, and 5 U mL⁻¹ penicillin, 50 μg streptomycin mL⁻¹. Cells were maintained at 37°C under 5% CO₂ atmosphere. To assess viability of cells in direct contact with the PEDOT:Lignosulfonate composite thin-films, cells were seeded onto the samples at a density of 50 000 cells/well and incubated for 24 h. To evaluate potential interference of the PEDOT:Lignosulfonate composite with the testing method, wells with the samples and without cell were included. After the incubation period, the supernatants containing detached cells were collected. Remaining cells were washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS; 0.1 M, pH 7.4) and detached by incubation with 0.25 % trypsin-EDTA solution (Gibco) for 5 min at 37°C. Cells were collected in cell culture medium and added to the supernatants. PBS from the washing step was also collected and added to the supernatants. Cell viability was assessed using a LIVE/DEAD Viability/Cytotoxicity Kit (Invitrogen) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Collected cells were stained with propidium iodide (PI, 10 μg mL⁻¹) and calcein-AM (50 μM diluted in DMSO) for 30 min at room temperature, protected from light. The fluorescence signal was measured on the BD FACSVerse flow cytometer (BD, San Jose, CA, USA) using the first two scatters (Forward scatter channel vs. Side scatter channel) and two fluorescence channels (red FL 2: ex. 488/em. 700 nm marking dead cells that lost membrane integrity, and green FL 3: ex. 488/em. 527 nm marking live cells with active intracellular esterases that catalyze the non-fluorescent calcein-AM to highly fluorescent green calcein. Three independent experiments were performed and mean and standard deviation ± (SD) were calculated.

4.9 | Cell Viability—Extracts (ISO 10993-5)

The ISO 10993-5 guideline for In vitro cytotoxicity evaluation of medical devices was followed to determine toxicity of the material extracts. Briefly, the PEDOT:LigS composite thin films on glass were incubated in 0.5 mL of DMEM cell culture medium for 24 h at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Cell culture medium maintained under the same conditions without the addition of the tested materials was used as the negative control. L929 cells were seeded at a density of 50 000 cells per well in a 24-well plate and allowed to get attached overnight. The cells culture medium was replaced with the extracts and incubated for 24 h, followed by the LIVE/DEAD assay performed as described above.

4.10 | Fluorescence Microscopy Imaging

Visual determination of the cell morphology and adhesion was performed by using microscope Olympus IX 70 in a fluorescence mode. Cells were prepared the same as for viability testing. After 24 and 72 h of incubation the medium was washed and replaced

with fresh medium containing fluorescent labels calcein-AM at the final concentration of 50 μM , respectively, diluted in DMSO. After 30 min incubation in the dark, the medium was replaced with PBS buffer and cells were imaged by optical fluorescent microscope.

Author Contributions

K.M. and S.T. conceptualized the study, led the experiments, and evaluated the overall data. T.G. conducted the material synthesis, optimized the material concentrations. K.M. and T.G. performed material characterization and analysis. T.G. obtained preliminary and drop-cast device results. K.M. fabricated and characterized glass- and paper-based OECTs. S.H. and K.P. performed the biocompatibility tests. M.C. carried out XPS measurements. K.M. developed and assembled degradable devices. A.O. (CATRIN, CZ) conducted fluorescence microscopy experiments. A.O. (UNIPI, IT) obtained the SEM measurements. K.M. designed and prepared the visual content. N.S.S. and S.T. received the funding to initiate the project. K.M. and S.T. co-wrote the original draft. S.T. wrote the final manuscript including the revisions. S.T. conceived the research and supervised the work. All authors reviewed and edited the final draft.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

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